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Abstract: *Gender differences in the use of language have become a common problem in daily conversations in our lives. When we use language regularly we often create differences between each other. These differences usually occurs between men and women. Gender difference in speech became an important issue of research within the field of sociolinguistics in the twentieth century. Therefore, as a much-debated topic for years, a large number of studies have been conducted on the gender-bound language use in various languages. Since language is an enormous area of study, various aspects of language have been covered; from the purpose of language employment to different language patterns commonly used by men and women.*

Key words: *gender-bound language, cross-cultural variability, linguistic system, classification, gender-based principles.*

Аннотация: *Гендерные различия в использовании языка стали распространенной проблемой в повседневных разговорах в нашей жизни. Когда мы регулярно используем язык, мы часто создаем различия между собой. Эти различия обычно возникают между мужчинами и женщинами. Гендерные различия в речи стали важным вопросом исследований в области социолингвистики двадцатого века. Поэтому, поскольку тема широко обсуждалась в течение многих лет, было проведено большое количество исследований гендерного использования языка в различных языках. Поскольку язык — это огромная область изучения, были охвачены различные аспекты языка; от цели использования языка до различных языковых моделей, обычно используемых мужчинами и женщинами.*

Ключевые слова: *гендерно-ориентированный язык, межкультурная изменчивость, языковая система, классификация, гендерные принципы.*

The huge cross-cultural variability in the speech styles associated with men and women is used to support a social learning explanation of gender differences in language use. As Gal, an anthropological linguist, pointed out, “male and female” differences in speech have been found in every society studied; but the nature of the contrasts is staggeringly diverse, occurring in varying parts of the linguistic system: phonology, pragmatics, syntax, morphology, and lexicon’.⁹ A commonly cited example used to

⁹ Tannen D. You just don’t understand. Women and men in conversation. N. Y., 1990.

highlight the cultural diversity is Keenan's research which found that, in contrast to Anglo-American cultural norms of speech for men and women, Malagasy men characteristically use indirect, ornate, more polite speech, while women use a more direct and straightforward style. Cross-cultural variability in the speech styles associated with men and women validates explanations emphasizing the importance of socialization processes for the development of gender-appropriate language use.¹⁰

Gender is the most complex of the grammatical categories. This is a topic of interest to non-linguists and linguists alike, and the more research there is, the more interesting it becomes. In some languages, gender is important and universal, in others it is not at all. One of his calls to linguists is that gender research has an interesting place in all important areas of language. Even in the short term, work in this area promises to be fruitful and address gender issues in second language learning. In the long run, the study of gender is very important in at least two places: First, it can show in which grammatical groups the subjects fall. Gender is the most confusing grammatical category. This is a topic of interest to non-linguists and linguists alike, and the more research there is, the more interesting it becomes. In some languages, gender is important and universal, in others it is not at all. One of his calls to linguists is that gender research has an interesting place in all important areas of language. Even in the short term, work in this area promises to be fruitful and address gender issues in second language learning. In the long run, gender studies are important for at least two purposes: First, they can show how the brain is talking; The second is specifically related to natural language processing, which removes local ambiguity in description. To understand what linguists call "gender", Hockett's definition is a good starting point: "Gender is a category of nouns that is reflected in the behavior of related words." A language may have two or more such groups or genders. This classification usually corresponds, at least in part, to the difference between the sexes, but often does not ("gender" is etymologically derived from the Latin Old French gender meaning "good" or "class"). The word "gender" is not used for a group of nouns, but for the entire group; hence we can say that a language has three aspects namely male, female and neutral and the language has a gender group.

Gender discourse now plays an important role in the creation of social discourse. Modern society has created gender lines. There are many differences between formal and informal sentences. This should be taken into account. Gender matters, and it goes without saying that gender issues have become important in giving meaning to many conversations. The concept of "gender linguistics" is used today as one of the most important problems of modern linguistics. Therefore, gender language is often understood as language that affects women or gender. In English, this includes using gender-specific terms such as "businessman" or "caretaker" to refer to jobs or people, or, for most people,

¹⁰ Freeman R. & McElhinny B. Language and Gender.// Sociolinguistics and Language Teaching, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.1996.

the use of male speech (he, she, it), such as "what the doctor should do". I know how to communicate with patients. "

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The use of gendered language, like the examples above, perpetuates what academic Allyson Jule calls 'the historical patriarchal hierarchy that has existed between men and women, where one (man) is considered the norm, and the other (woman) is marked as other – as something quite different from the norm'.

Men and women have different preferences in choosing topics during relationships. Most men choose politics, business, products, sports, current news and other topics when talking. Women, children's education, clothing, cooking, fashion, etc. When they like to talk about family like. While women's speech is associated with domestic and domestic activities, men's speech is associated with the outside world and work. So, while there may be a bias that women talk more than men, social research on a variety of situations, such as social groups and Internet discussion groups, shows that the opposite is true. Women may talk more than men in informal settings, but in formal settings they play a secondary role and tend to talk less than men. Sociolinguists have investigated women's silence in society and the work they do in their relationships (Spender, 1980). In addition to this difference, there are other differences between genders; For example, men and women will have different sentences and different movements and gestures.

There are some important problems that should be discussed in the terms of gender. There are some significant differences in how language develops and how people tend to express themselves based on gender. As a whole, women tend to use language more relationally, or in the context of close relationships with others. Each discourse can have various impacts on social groups with the same content due to different gender-based principles. Thus, gender issues should be taken into consideration to focus on any discourse, speech or context to deal it with more specific linguistic features.

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